

Participant	Game	Assigned Pattern	Playtime
P01	<i>Celeste</i>	Open Gate	Over 10 hours
P06	<i>God of War: Ragnarok</i>	Adaptive Challenge	Over 10 hours
P07	<i>Shadow of the Tomb Raider</i>	Visual Support	Over 10 hours
P07	<i>Minecraft</i>	Creative Suite	Over 10 hours
P08	<i>Teamfight Tactics (TFT)</i>	Companion	Over 10 hours
P09	<i>Metroid Dread</i>	Progression	Over 10 hours